

THE MAIN FORMS OF COMPLEMENTING THE EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN THE LIVES OF STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Extracurricular and out-of-school educational activities complement the educational activities in the lives of students. Therefore, it is necessary to effectively organize such educational work and make the right choice.

It is well known that today's evolving world requires students not to be limited to schooling. At this time, it is advisable to organize extracurricular and extracurricular activities. In 1993, the concept of "Extracurricular and Extracurricular Activities" was approved by the Ministry of Public Education. With the adoption of the National Training Program and the Law on Education, the concept was revised and approved by the Board of the Ministry of Public Education on July 30, 1999 No. 8/5. Undoubtedly, such work in the field of education is aimed at the development of today's young people into a comprehensively developed person: school community, family and community organizations are equally responsible for this process. Human development is a very complex and continuous process. It is important to focus on the child's personality and to make effective use of the

social experience gained over the years. Extracurricular and out-of-school educational activities are primarily aimed at the meaningful organization of students' free time after school, which serves to develop in them such qualities as organization, initiative, entrepreneurship. Extracurricular activities include: a) science clubs b) carpentry clubs c) crafts clubs d) sports clubs e) amateur art clubs. as a successor to music schools. Extracurricular and out-of-school educational activities are optional, based on students' interests and desires, or recommended by the class teacher and youth leader. The educational impact of extracurricular activities depends on the level of effective organization of the learning process and how and to what extent the student body organizes the various activities. Students perceive, process, and generate new knowledge

outside of the classroom. Extracurricular activities develop students' ability to work in a team. Class teachers also play an important role in the formation of extracurricular activities. In secondary schools, clubs are organized by the class teacher or the organizer of educational work. Involves them in a circle. Through these circles, students put their theoretical knowledge into practice. The person who organizes extracurricular activities should also be an example to students in terms of defined activities. Therefore, the role of the educator is multifaceted. Her unique lessons, rich in interesting scenes, increase the interest and spirituality of the students. It is advisable for educators and class teachers to use the following methods in their educational work outside the classroom and outside of school:

1. Oral methods. Various news, meetings, morning meetings, lectures, readers'

conferences, discussions, meetings, newspapers, radio magazines. 2. Methods of practical work. Trips to different places, sports competitions, Olympics, athletics, young naturalists' clubs, Saturdays. 3. Demonstration work methods. School museums, War and Labor Heroes Room, new book exhibitions. These methods also stimulate students' interest in science and bring them into a cultural environment.

In short, out-of-class and out-of-school educational activities not only complement the educational activities of students, but also prepare young people for free thinking, help them understand the meaning of life, develop self-management and control, and develop unity of plan and practice. development activities. In general, such educational work is characterized by the focus on the maturity of the individual, his bright future.

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